

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan

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ABSTRACT

The *D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan* deliverable addresses the need for a dedicated regulation for service quality standards and evaluation procedures in E-RIHS ERIC, as required by Art. 7.3 of the E-RIHS Statutes.

It serves as a comprehensive framework for E-RIHS's quality management. It integrates two core components: the policy and the operational procedures, ensuring a cohesive approach to quality assurance and continuous improvement. The **quality policy** establishes the strategic principles and objectives, while the **operational procedures** provide the practical instructions and **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to implement these principles. Together, they function as a cohesive **quality manual**, ensuring that the system combines strategic direction with actionable processes to maintain high standards across E-RIHS activities in alignment with E-RIHS mission.

The practical procedures provide a cohesive structure to assess and enhance quality across all activities and outputs associated with E-RIHS, including access provisions, training initiatives, and external endorsements. Refined and tested over time by the E-RIHS community, they set objectives, define scope and expectations, and assign responsibilities. They adopt a flexible approach, enabling adaptations to diverse operational environments within National Nodes, while ensuring compliance with E-RIHS's overarching quality principles.

The KPIs have been tailored to effectively monitor progress against achievable targets as E-RIHS ERIC begins operations. These targets may be refined once E-RIHS transitions to a steady state of operations, ensuring performance is tracked, outcomes are assessed, and continuous improvement is achieved.

The deliverable also incorporates the foundational *E-RIHS Ethics Guidelines*, aligned with the ALLEA Code of Conduct, addressing individual, interpersonal, societal, and environmental ethics to ensure E-RIHS's credibility and reputation. These guidelines are expected to evolve over time to reflect advancements in research practices and emerging technologies.

As E-RIHS evolves, this quality plan is designed to be a living document, regularly updated to reflect technological advancements, regulatory changes, and lessons learned from ongoing operations. This approach ensures that E-RIHS maintains the highest standards of quality, enhances credibility, support its long-term sustainability, and remains at the forefront of research excellence in service provision, fostering innovation and driving impactful contributions to the heritage science community.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronyms	Expansion
ALLEA	All European Academies
ARCHLAB	ARCHive LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CC-NC license	Creative Commons – Non-Commercial license
CC0	CC0 1.0 Universal (Creative Commons deed with no-copyright dedication)
CNN	Committee of National Nodes
DIGILAB	DIGItal LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that provides remote access to heritage science data, supplemented with digital services and tools within a virtual research environment (under development)
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung (German Standardization Institute)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DSA	Data Seal of Approval (a self-assessment process for digital archives, aimed at archives that hold data)
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FIXLAB	FIXed LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together fixed research facilities and associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
GPL	General Public Licence
HS Academy	E-RIHS training program in heritage science delivered through various formats, including doctoral summer schools, on-site training camps, webinars, lecture series, and specialized modules. The program is designed for both E-RIHS users and providers.
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KER	Key Evaluator Ratings (average of scores attributed by a team of evaluators appointed by the E-RIHS management on a scale of 1–poor to 10–excellent, corresponding to a quantification of subjective appraisals of the quality level of the feature examined)
KPI	Key Performance Indicators (values that may be objectively measured allowing an unbiased appraisal of operational effectiveness)
MOLAB	Mobile LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together European laboratories offering state-of-the-art mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
NC	Non-Commercial
NN	National Node
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
RG	Research Group (any individualized group of researchers and technical support active in the context of E-RIHS).
SEAB	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board

INTRODUCTION

The *D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan* deliverable serves as a comprehensive framework for E-RIHS's quality management. It integrates two core components: the policy and the operational procedures, ensuring a cohesive approach to quality assurance and continuous improvement. The **quality policy** establishes the strategic principles and objectives, while the **operational procedures** provide the practical instructions and **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to implement these principles. Together, they function as a cohesive **quality manual**, ensuring that the system combines strategic direction with actionable processes to maintain high standards across E-RIHS activities in alignment with E-RIHS mission.

The document builds upon previous deliverables (Mimoso et al., 2020; Mimoso & Doherty, 2021; Doherty et al., 2023; Doherty, Costa & Mimoso, 2024), by integrating tested and refined procedures developed collaboratively by the E-RIHS community, consolidating them into a coherent quality system plan. It is the result of the work carried out in task T3.4 in E-RIHS IP, involving various exchanges and meetings among task participants, project partners, members of the interim Committee of National Nodes, and specific discussions with E-RIHS communities operating at the national level. The work aimed at finalizing the quality system plan to ensure its smooth implementation once E-RIHS ERIC enters its operational phase. It was also executed through testing the viability of the quality assessment procedures presented in this document.

From the perspective of the *E-RIHS Quality Policy* outlining the commitment to quality, the document outlines standardized procedures and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) essential for ensuring consistent and high-quality operations. It provides objectives, defines scope and expectations, and assigns responsibilities, all tailored to accommodate the diverse operational environments within E-RIHS and designed to uniform excellence across all services provided by each provider and National Node. Additionally, it includes ethical guidelines to uphold the integrity and credibility of all E-RIHS activities.

Six annexes further detail specific procedures and tools, including Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), to support the quality assurance system.

PROCEDURES AND TOOLS OF E-RIHS QUALITY SYSTEM

The six annexes outline operational procedures and tools for E-RIHS quality system and include the following:

Annex I. E-RIHS Access Service Quality Assessment Forms

- I.1 Candidate Provider Form;
- I.2 New Service Assessment Form;
- I.3 Periodic Provider Self-Assessment Form;
- I.4 Recommendation Form for New Services;
- I.5 Assessment Form for Existing Services.

Annex II. E-RIHS ERIC Endorsement: Request and Letter Templates

Annex III. E-RIHS DIGITAL Services Quality Assessment

Annex IV. KPIs and Datasheets

Annex V. Examples of E-RIHS Satisfaction Feedback Forms

Annex VI. E-RIHS Ethics Guidelines

The annexes serve as practical instruments to implement, monitor, and evaluate quality assurance processes across E-RIHS. Forms and templates provide structured and standardized methods for data collection, assessment, and reporting, ensuring consistency and clarity. KPIs act as measurable tools to evaluate performance, track progress, and guide continuous improvement. Additionally, narratives and guidelines offer clear instructions and frameworks to support effective implementation and decision-making. Full quality system implementation is expected to be achieved through a gradual roll-out of procedures with necessary tweaking for optimum operability, accompanied by coherent monitoring to assess effectiveness and to identify any deficiencies. Continuous improvement is expected to be achieved through feedback mechanisms, corrective actions, and strategic periodic reviews.

As E-RIHS ERIC becomes operational, it is expected that reporting methods will evolve digitally, enabling more efficient data collection and visualization. This will facilitate centralized tracking of trends, highlight areas for improvement, and ensure ongoing transparency.

Last but not least, this deliverable addresses the need for a dedicated regulation for service quality standards and evaluation procedures in E-RIHS ERIC, as required by Art. 7.3 of the E-RIHS Statutes. As such, it will be submitted to the E-RIHS General Assembly for approval.

E-RIHS QUALITY POLICY

E-RIHS, *the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, is a distributed infrastructure integrating national facilities of recognized excellence. E-RIHS connects researchers in arts, humanities, science and engineering and fosters a transdisciplinary culture of exchange and cooperation.

E-RIHS is dedicated to delivering exceptional services and fostering scientific excellence across all its distributed National Nodes. E-RIHS's commitment to quality is central to its mission of advancing collaborative research and ensuring that users, providers, and stakeholders benefit from the highest standards of innovation, reliability, and ethical integrity.

E-RIHS intends to maintain consistency across all National Nodes by ensuring that all services and their outputs meet the set quality criteria. Each National Node is held to the same high standards of operational performance.

The needs of users and stakeholders are prioritized through continuous adaptation to their evolving expectations through active engagement and feedback. By listening to its user community, E-RIHS strives to deliver research support while fostering collaboration and open communication across the network.

E-RIHS is built on a foundation of continuous improvement, with regular monitoring driving its commitment to quality, ensuring that best practices are widely adopted. E-RIHS is equally committed to sustainability, supporting cutting-edge research innovation that contribute to long-term scientific and societal goals.

This *E-RIHS Quality Policy* applies to all National Nodes, personnel, and providers, guiding the central approach to quality management. By adhering to this policy, E-RIHS aims to be a leader in providing exceptional research services and ensuring that E-RIHS is recognized for its excellence and contribution to global scientific advancements.

1. E-RIHS Service Quality

Quality is one of the pillars of E-RIHS and to ensure its high-level, set quality criteria must be met by all organizations and research groups connected to the E-RIHS brand identity or using the E-RIHS label. However, as a general note, "quality" must be understood throughout the E-RIHS network as a standard of excellence established by the ERIC with a view to ensure: (i) the will and the means to satisfy the users of its services; (ii) consistency between its providers, particularly in respect to operational procedures and their results; (iii) register and store of all preliminary steps, metrological conditions and results related with any service rendered, allowing its inclusion in a digital database or replication in any other laboratory. E-RIHS ERIC shall coordinate the community of National Nodes including the establishment and monitoring of quality management procedures for the National Nodes and the provider facilities. Thus, it is expected that the indicated assessment procedures be provided by the central coordination yet upheld at the National Node level through reporting to the Central Hub and established timelines.

This document represents the minimum quality manual content to be prepared and maintained collaboratively by the Central Hub and all National Nodes and their providers. The quality manual aims at being an in-house reference document, which has been made as brief and non-bureaucratic as possible. An updated copy should be easily accessible to those directly involved in E-RIHS operations. The manual may also be made available on request to users and may in general be

diffused to give confidence in the work done and its results. National Nodes are free to increase the contents or alter their disposition as they consider fit for its purpose.

In all cases, the contents of this document comprising the quality manual does not need duplicate the contents of any other manual applicable to the service. Therefore, the manual as prescribed may be simplified if the institution is accredited or certified for the service rendered by a standard such as ISO 17025 (ISO/IEC 17025, 2017) or ISO 9001 (ISO 9001, 2015) and already holds a quality or procedures manual where the full information may be found.

2. E-RIHS Quality Assessment

On a general note, “quality” is understood as an evaluation from the specific E-RIHS perspective as a degree to which distinct criteria are maintained within the research infrastructure. Given the varied nature of the services to which the quality assessment will apply, the procedures presented herein require flexibility. It must be noted that the procedures must not be considered as a bureaucratic compliance verification exercise but rather as a collaborative process between all parties involved with a common goal to ensure E-RIHS quality.

Quality assessment is required for ALL services offered by E-RIHS, starting with access services, which include excellence-driven access, wide access procedures to prospective modes such as matchmaking services, market-drive access, thematic access calls (Etgens et al, 2024). The assessment applies both existing providers through periodic reviews, candidates seeking to become new providers or external institutions aiming to establish collaboration with E-RIHS. It will also be used to evaluate services such as HS Academy training activities (Andrews & Grau-Bove, J., 2024) and may extend to communication and dissemination initiatives (Benassi et al., 2024) and events proposed by non-E-RIHS organizations seeking an endorsement from E-RIHS. Last but not least, the quality assessment already impacts certain Central Hub’s activities (Striova et al, 2024), with potential for further development.

2.1 PROCEDURES FOR ACCESS SERVICES

The E-RIHS access services are offered by *providers* granting access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, archives, data and specialized knowledge for advancing science and technologies in the field of heritage science.

The E-RIHS quality assessment procedures for access services (see Annex I.1—5) starts on the initiative of a provider contacting its National Node and proposing new services, or of a prospective new provider (“candidate”) contacting the E-RIHS Central Hub and being referred to its National Node. Regarding periodic provider reviews, assessment is carried out at national level according to Central Hub coordination and set timeframe.

Table 1: Application of E-RIHS access services quality assessment procedures according to institution type and subject.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURE	PROVIDERS	NEW PROVIDER CANDIDATE
Overall quality assessment	Yearly periodic assessment (Annex I.3)	Admission (Annex I.1)

New services offered	Simplified procedure (Annex I.2)	Full procedure, jointly with admission procedure (Annexes I.1 and I.2)
Feedback on services rendered	Continued assessment at National Node – data provided to Central Hub annually or on request	The means for monitoring feedback should be in place on acceptance into E-RIHS

2.1.1 Overview of Steps for E-RIHS Access Service Quality Assessment

The procedure for assessing the quality of providers or candidate providers, as well as the services they provide or propose to provide through E-RIHS is carried out in a sequence of steps. Guidelines for each step and, where applicable, the Key Performance Indicators chosen for continuing appraisal will be published by E-RIHS and made available to all institutions undertaking the procedure.

The complete procedural steps are as follows.

STEP 1: EX-ANTE QUALITY ASSESSMENT [only for candidate provider]

This step aims at evaluating the existence and correctness of the candidate’s internal processes, including governance, management and administration. This step may be skipped or simplified if the institution is accredited / certified by a standard such as ISO 17025 or ISO 9001. Verification of financial viability is also part of this step; it may be omitted for public institutions.

Annex I.1 is filled out and declared by the candidate provider, submitted to the National Node and, if positively assessed, sent to the Central Hub for record-keeping.

The assessment is carried out by the quality representative at the National Node or the National Node Coordinator, who retains overall responsibility. Each Node may organize this process as it sees fit, provided it aligns with the E-RIHS Quality Policy and its criteria.

STEP 2: DOCUMENTATION OF EXISTING AND PROPOSED NEW SERVICES

This step focuses on collecting documentation of existing services or those proposed for new inclusion by current providers or candidate providers. The objective is to gather comprehensive information on the relevance of these services to the aims of E-RIHS, their adherence to E-RIHS’ vision and mission and ethical guidelines as well as the actual or expected demand by the heritage science community for such service/s.

Annex I.2 is to be filled out by provider, candidate provider or service manager (i.e., the contact person managing access at a provider's facility) for proposing any NEW access services for the Catalogue of Services.

Existing services already offered by providers are monitored yearly through **Annex I.3**.

The forms Annex I.2 and Annex I.3 are sent by the quality representative at the National Node or the National Node Coordinator, who retains overall responsibility, to the Central Hub for record-keeping.

STEP 3: ASSESSMENT

STEP 3a: Peer review assessment [only for proposed new services]

This step evaluates proposed new services through a peer review process that follows established academic good practices for scientific reviews. The evaluation is based on the information provided in Annex I.2, and the assessment uses **Annex I.4**.

STEP 3b: Periodic assessment [only for existing services]

This step focuses on the periodic assessment of services already included in E-RIHS on the basis of the information provided in Annex I-3. The quality representative or National Node Coordinator, who holds overall responsibility, uses this data to fill out Assessment Forms for Existing Services (**Annex I.5**). The Central Hub compiles a **periodic assessment summary report** on the basis of the collected forms.

Both the peer review and periodic assessments are performed by the Scientific and Ethics Advisory board (SEAB), assisted by the Committee of National Nodes (see the E-RIHS ERIC Statutes Art. 7.1-2). If required, an ad hoc committee (Statutes, Art. 18.6c) may also be involved. The **recommendation report** generated during these steps – Annex I.4 for each new service and comments based on the periodic assessment summary report for existing services – is provided to the Committee of National Nodes to inform their decision on approval and implementation.

STEP 4: APPROVAL AND IMPLEMENTATION

STEP 4a: Approval of new providers and services

The final decision of addition of new services and candidate providers with new services will be made by the E-RIHS CNN as part of their task to prepare the annual offer of services (see E-RIHS ERIC Statutes Art. 20.3.f) based on the recommendation report from Step 3a.

The Committee of National Nodes is free to organize internally as it deems appropriate to finalize the decision, provided it acts in good faith and solely in the best interest of E-RIHS. An **evaluation report** will be prepared and transmitted to the E-RIHS Director General to enable the Central Hub to inform the respective providers or candidate providers and implement the decision.

The decision may be one of the following:

- a) *Approved*;
- b) *Rejected, with justification*;
- c) *Approved with recommendations*: This is the case where minor issues are noted, but they are expected to be amended in the short term; the evaluation report will indicate a plan for corrections. Final approval is then subject to the verification of successful compliance to such plan.

d) *Pending*: In this case E-RIHS sees a potential for the candidate but major issues prevent the immediate approval of the candidature. The final report will sketch out a roadmap to acceptance and will indicate, when appropriate, tutor organizations chosen within the partnership to accompany and guide the candidate to achieve full compliance. Final approval is subject to a renewed quality assessment of the candidate provider and/or the proposed new service.

Probation Period

Approved new providers and services are subject to a period of probation of at least 12 months. Following such, the service undergoes periodic assessment, and the relevant National Node Coordinator recommends to the Committee of National Nodes:

- (i) a positive conclusion,
- (ii) an extension of the probation for a further period or
- (iii) a negative result.

The CNN decides on the outcome of the process and communicates to the E-RIHS Director General to enable the Central Hub carries out the relevant communications.

STEP 4b: Periodic quality review for existing providers and services

The periodic quality review focuses on the annual activities of existing providers and services within E-RIHS, primarily based on Annex I.3 and Annex I.5 documentation. On-site visits and interviews may be conducted if deemed necessary. Exclusion proposals are considered only in cases of significant non-compliance or defaults and must be justified and motivated by substantial evidence.

2.2.2 Scenarios Requiring Quality Assessment

The above process applies in part or wholly to the various assessment scenarios, as detailed below.

i. Inclusion of a new provider and service/s

The process of the acceptance of a new provider includes Step 1 (Annex I.1), Step 2 (Annex I.2) applied to all proposed services, Step 3a (Annex I.4) and Step 4a. Additionally, it includes an evaluation of the in-kind contribution associated with these services.

ii. Periodic quality assessment of existing providers and services

The process for quality assessment of existing providers and services follows a simplified procedure that omits Step 1 and includes Steps 2 (Annex I.3), Step 3b (Annex I.5) and Step 4b.

iii. New services offered by existing providers

The quality assessment of new services, including the evaluation of their in-kind contribution, are carried out by applying Step 2 (Annex I.2), Step 3a (Annex I.4) and Step 4a, focusing exclusively on the proposed new service/s. Step 1 is not required.

Table 2: Quality control features for each category assessed.

ACTIVITY SUBJECT TO QUALITY ASSESSMENT	QUALITY CONTROL FEATURES	
	PROVIDER	CANDIDATE PROVIDER
Inclusion as new provider	N/A	Step 1
Inclusion of new service/s	Steps 2, 3a and 4a, assessed only as regards the new service/s. Minimum one-year probation.	Steps 3a and 4a, assessed for each new service. Minimum one year probation.
Periodic quality assessment	Steps 2, 3b and 4b.	N/A

2.3 PROCEDURES FOR TRAINING INITIATIVES

While it is likely that the organization of training initiatives will often originate within the Central Hub (as outlined in *D2.5 Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices*), with the host being decided through a competitive selection process, it is possible that National Nodes may want to organize their own ‘self-proposed’ training events under HS Academy branding, sometimes within national languages. As emphasised in *D4.5 Revised Training Strategy*, it is clear that there needs to be a process for ensuring the quality and conformity of these events; this has been proposed below:

- The training personnel within the Central Hub should be made aware of the ‘self-proposed’ training event at the earliest stage in preparations.
- Before any advertising has been undertaken, a draft programme should be submitted to the Central Hub so that checks can be made that the course aims, content, delivery, and speakers align with E-RIHS’ objectives.
- In the first year of running, ‘self-proposed’ training courses should be identified as ‘Pilots’ and must be attended by an official E-RIHS observer – ideally the member of staff responsible for overseeing training – and formal feedback as to the suitability of the course and recommendations for future iterations must be provided to the hosts. Feedback is to be collected timely from participants.
- Following the approval of the event by an E-RIHS representative, a reasonable re-observation strategy should be put in place based on the frequency of the course.

It is also possible that training may be offered as a service by providers. The principles of the quality system must be adapted to effectively monitor training services, ensuring that they meet the standards of excellence expected by all E-RIHS services.

2.4 PROCEDURES FOR UNFORESEEN AND EXTERNAL NEEDS

2.4.1 Endorsement Process for External Initiatives and Organization

E-RIHS provides formal endorsement to initiatives, projects, or entities that align with its mission, vision, and values, supporting impactful contributions to the heritage science community. For external needs not covered by existing quality assessment cases, a structured process is followed to

evaluate and grant endorsement. Request for endorsement (**Annex II.1**), addressed to the Director General (DG) and the Chair of the Committee of National Nodes (CNN), should include key details about the project/initiative, such as its title, abstract, objectives, and relevance to E-RIHS's goals. The DG and Chair CNN, in consultation with committee members if needed, evaluate the proposal, ensuring it does not conflict with other E-RIHS initiatives. Upon positive evaluation and absence of conflicts of interest, the DG issues an endorsement letter (**Annex II.2**), which may include permission to use E-RIHS branding. Regular updates may be requested to monitor the project's progress and sustained alignment with E-RIHS standards, ensuring that the endorsement remains a mark of quality and commitment to excellence within the heritage science community.

2.4.2 Unforeseen Cases

Cases not included in the categories listed above or unforeseen circumstances are to be addressed by the quality officer/s at the Central Hub and National Nodes using as a basis the principles and procedures set by this document with the necessary adaptations.

3. Resources Allocation and Costs

D3.1 E-RIHS ERIC Human Resources Strategy and Procedures has identified that a role supporting the implementation of the E-RIHS quality system will be established within the core Central Hub team at the initial operation of the ERIC. This role involves coordinating quality assessment procedures, ensuring compliance with E-RIHS standards, and aligning practices across National Nodes with the Quality Policy and Manual. The Quality Officer also serves as a point of contact for National Nodes, providing guidance and support to ensure consistent application of quality criteria throughout the infrastructure. In addition to overseeing quality procedures, the dedicated staff unit will monitor the costs incurred by E-RIHS related to quality assessment activities, including staff time, travel expenses and eventual payments to external members. Special cases such as courses, summer schools, organized by non-E-RIHS institutions may be exempt from monitoring costs, but subject to special conditions, such as offering discounted registration fees to E-RIHS providers.

4. Approval and Revision

The E-RIHS Quality Policy with its Manual and Plan will be effective upon approval by the General Assembly of E-RIHS ERIC. E-RIHS Quality Policy and its Manual may be reviewed annually, provided any proposed amendments are finalized and submitted before the General Assembly meeting where the yearly Plan is presented.

Annual KPI results should be considered, and any proposed changes have to be clearly justified and presented alongside the yearly Plan.

If updates to the Quality Manual are required, the affected sections are replaced.

It is the responsibility of the quality representative at each National Node or the National Node Coordinator, who retains overall responsibility for aligning the national quality assessment with the E-RIHS ERIC requirements, to ensure that the Manual is kept up to date and available to providers.

ANNEX I. E-RIHS ACCESS SERVICE QUALITY ASSESSMENT FORMS

Annex I includes the forms to be used in three of the four steps of the quality assessment process for access services for both providers and candidate providers.

They are:

ANNEX	WHO [COMPILED BY]	PROCEDURE
I.1 Candidate Provider Form [STEP1: EX-ANTE QUALITY ASSESSMENT]	Candidate provider	Reviewed by NN quality representative/Coordinator. Sent to the Central Hub.
I.2 New Service Assessment Form [STEP 2: DOCUMENTATION]	Provider / candidate provider or service manager	Reviewed by NN quality representative/Coordinator. Sent to the Central Hub.
I.3 Periodic Provider Self-Assessment Form [STEP 2: DOCUMENTATION]	Provider	Reviewed by NN quality representative/Coordinator. Sent to the Central Hub for record-keeping.
I.4 Recommendation Form for New Services [STEP 3: ASSESSMENT]	SEAB assisted by CNN/ ad hoc committee	Sent to CNN.
I.5 Assessment Form for Existing Services [STEP 3: ASSESSMENT]	NN quality representative/ Coordinator	Sent to the Central Hub. Periodic assessment summary report sent to SEAB, assisted by NNC/ad hoc committee.

Prospective partnerships with E-RIHS often involve only a specific division or a research group within an organization. While most assessments will focus on the relevant unit, critical aspects such as decision-making processes,, financial viability, and technical or administrative management, must be evaluated at the organizational level (Annex I.1).

The new service assessment is aimed to apply to candidate providers, proposing to offer access to E-RIHS services (Annex I.2).

Selected Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are also incorporated within the periodic assessment of providers’ services (Annex I.5) to be objectively measured, allowing an unbiased calculation of operational effectiveness. All E-RIHS KPIs instead are presented as a stand-alone document (see Annex IV).

The assessment of data-related services for digital access is provisionally addressed separately in Annex III and will be fully revised after the DIGILAB platform is finalized.

I.1 Candidate Provider Form

Annex I.1 is filled out and declared by the candidate provider, submitted to the National Node and, if positively assessed, sent to the Central Hub. The assessment is carried out by the quality representative at the National Node or the National Node Coordinator, who retains overall responsibility.

Institution: _____

NOTE: Please add relevant institution; department; laboratory.

Contact Person: [Name, Surname] _____, [e-mail, phone] _____

[Position within institution] _____

NOTE: Please add Name, Contact and position within institution

National Node: _____

Decision-making and administrative procedures and policies			
	YES	NO	COMMENTS
Is the institution accredited / certified by a standard (e.g.: ISO 17025, ISO 9001, etc)? If yes, please indicate your accreditations / certifications.			
Is the decision-making chain clearly defined within the institution?			
Is there an accounting system in place, providing detailed information on costs and suitable to extract data relevant for in-kind contribution assessment?			
Are administrative procedures well-defined and applicable to the proposed services?			
Are the above aspects formally described in internal documents such as a manual of procedures?			
Are personnel informed of their responsibilities regarding work within E-RIHS?			

Internal policies and their compliance with EU strategies			
	YES	NO	COMMENTS
Is there a digital data policy for the documentation of heritage science data (when applicable)?			
Is there an Open Access data policy in force for raw data and publications?			
Adherence to EU policies concerning employees			
	YES	NO	COMMENTS
Health and safety at work?			
Equal opportunities for women and men?			
Protection against discrimination based on gender, race, religion, age, disability and sexual orientation?			
Informing and consulting employees?			
International experience pertinent to E-RIHS			
	YES	NO	COMMENTS
Has the organization experience in European cooperation?			
Does its international experience also extend relevantly outside Europe?			
Sustainability and financial viability			
	YES	NO	COMMENTS
Has the organization as a whole sufficient financial support to guarantee its continuity in the foreseeable future?			
Does it support the activities under E-RIHS ensuring its sustainability in the medium-long term (5 years minimum)?			

Signature

[Candidate provider]

I confirm that the information provided is true and accurate to the best of my knowledge.

Date _____

Name _____

Signature (handwritten or digital) _____

I.2 New Service Assessment Form

Annex I.2 is completed by providers, candidate providers, or service managers (i.e., the contact person managing access at a provider's facility) for each new service proposed for inclusion in E-RIHS. The document is submitted to the National Node quality representative or Coordinator for initial assessment and, once reviewed, forwarded to the E-RIHS Central Hub.

Provider: _____

NOTE. For new provider candidates please add relevant institution; department; laboratory.

National Node: _____

INSERT THE NAME OF THE NEW SERVICE SUBMITTED TO E-RIHS ASSESSMENT
FOR INSERTION TO PLATFORM
ARCHLAB <input type="checkbox"/> FIXLAB <input type="checkbox"/> MOLAB <input type="checkbox"/>

1. VALUE PROPOSITION

Does the proposed new service provide valuable research capabilities for E-RIHS that are currently unavailable within its network?

NOTE. If applicable, please write down what they are and how they may be used.

Is the proposed new service already available through E-RIHS but offer innovative, unique or very sought after applications or expertise?

NOTE. If applicable, please write down what these features are.

Based on experience of the facility, what is the expected demand for the service?

2. FACILITY AND EQUIPMENT

(Reply where applicable)

With the potential increase in users that a new service may attract, will there be sufficient space on the premises for users to sit, access computers, and carry out work related to the services?

NOTE: This question refers to ARCHLAB and FIXLAB services

Is the equipment appropriate for the planned activities?

NOTE: This question refers solely to the type of equipment and not the specific condition of the hardware e.g., to its metrological maintenance.

Are measurements, calibrations, and similar activities conducted in accordance with documented procedures, such as international standards, or alternative procedures when standards are unavailable?

Has the access provider (i.e. department or division in charge of the service) a previous good scientific / technical record in the relevant fields in the last five years?

What is the fitness for purpose of the equipment involved in the service? In particular:

Has the uncertainty of measurements been reckoned? If not, then how appropriate are:

- the instrumental resolution? _____
- its repeatability? _____
- its stated accuracy? _____

What is the status of limitative conditions? (e.g., what are the detection limits and which conditions, such as the matrix, may affect the results?)

Is there a regular metrological/maintenance scheme in place, with appropriate allocation of resources?

Are computing resources appropriate in terms of storage and processing power, so to accommodate the expected amount and nature of produced data from the new service?

3. PERSONNEL

Is the available staff trained, experienced and competent to assist users in the research activity associated with the new service e.g., choosing the correct analytical/computational method; considering its limitations; assessing and critically evaluating the results; and drawing the correct conclusions in accordance with proposed research questions?

NOTE 1: It is not required that the personnel ascribed to work under E-RIHS has knowledge of, e.g., all the materials/matrices they may have to analyse, but they should then be aware of their own limitations and know where within the partnership they may find the necessary capabilities.

4. SERVICE QUALITY

Does the proposed new service adhere to E-RIHS vision and mission and ethical guidelines (see annex 5)?

If applicable, are the equipment characteristics of the proposed new service appropriately documented and operating instructions available? Provide details

When instruments are offered for external access under E-RIHS, will the characteristics be available to users in English?

Has the access provider (i.e., department or division in charge of the proposed new services) a previous good scientific/technical record in the relevant fields in the last five years?

NOTE: Please add max.5 DOIs to relevant publications in peer-review journals to assess the expertise level of the department.

Signature

[provider/candidate provider or service manager]

I confirm that the information provided is true and accurate to the best of my knowledge.

Date _____

Name _____

Signature (handwritten or digital) _____

I.3 Periodic Provider Self-Assessment Form

Annex I.3 is completed annually by each E-RIHS provider, comprehensive of all services they offer within E-RIHS. The document is submitted to the National Node quality representative or Coordinator for assessment. Once reviewed, it is forwarded to the E-RIHS Central Hub and retained for future reference.

Provider: _____

National Node: _____

INSERT ID OF ALL SERVICES PROVIDED THROUGH E-RIHS (add rows as necessary)

1. FACILITIES AND EQUIPMENT

Is the infrastructure facility appropriate for the provision of E-RIHS services?

Is the equipment itself appropriate for the provision of E-RIHS services?

NOTE: This question refers solely to the type of equipment and not the specific condition of the hardware, e.g., to its metrological maintenance.

Are measurements and calibrations conducted according to international standards, or procedures to the same purpose when standards are not available?

2. PERSONNEL

Note if there have been any changes in personnel in the last year, confirm whether they are trained, experienced and competent to conduct (or to assist users in) offered research activity in accordance with proposed research questions, e.g., choosing the correct analytical/computational method; considering its limitations; assessing and critically evaluating the results; and drawing the correct conclusions?

NOTE 1: It is not required that the personnel ascribed to work under E-RIHS has knowledge of, e.g., all the materials/matrices they may have to analyse, but they should then be aware of their own limitations and know where within the partnership they may find the necessary capabilities.

NOTE 2: Please add DOIs to relevant publications in peer-review journals to ascertain the competency of new personnel.

Would personnel who are facilitating access to services be willing to undergo additional training offered by the partnership with E-RIHS?

If the answer to the above question was YES, in which areas would extra training be useful (e.g., scientific techniques/humanities research skills/digital analysis methods)?

3. SERVICE QUALITY AND RELEVANCE

Do services adhere to E-RIHS core values and ethical principles?

Concerning the previous 12 months, provide the KPI_{ACC} Access demand. For each service, what was the percentage of accesses demanded over the available slots of access? Please show your working out below in this format: (Access demanded/Available access) x100%?

NOTE: This KPI Verifies that there is demand for each service offered and that promotion of access is sufficient to attract a high inflow of interested researchers. Target: KPI > 100% at the end of any reference period.

SERVICE ID	No. of demands	No. of access slots	%

In the previous 12 months, what was the total number of accesses delivered?

What is the number of accesses currently planned but still to be delivered?

Insert the amount of time and human resource made available to each project. This should be recorded in access units, which may vary from precise values like hours or sessions of beam time to calendar days of access (one working day is considered to be 8 hours unless otherwise stated). Where the activity has involved more than one staff member, also indicate the number of staff involved with a base time per person.

NOTE 1: If more space is needed, create additional rows within the table.

NOTE 2: These values must match figures that are declared to the E-RIHS administration.

Project Acronym	SERVICE ID	Access to service	Support to user pre- and post-access	Data processing and elaborations	Report writing
xxxx example	xxxx	5 days	2 days	2 days each, 2 members of staff	2 days

4. FEEDBACK FROM USERS

Based on the E-RIHS satisfaction survey: What % of service accesses were rated higher than 8 (out of 10) by users?

NOTE: KPI_{ACC} 3. Access quality, by measuring: (Users rating satisfaction in top two categories / All users). 100% Objective: Appraise the quality of the service from the perspective of users Target: KPI > 80% after an initial probation period of 12 months.

NOTE 2: This question is only relevant for managed physical and digital services where access is dependent on a formal application (not an 'available' DIGILAB service).

What is your impression of the results received by your facility on consideration of the standard E-RIHS criterion (that on a 1 to 10 scale, at least 80% of users should rate satisfaction ≥ 8)?

NOTE: Please indicate whether actions have been taken following negative feedback.

5. SCIENTIFIC IMPACT

In the previous year, how many publications (full papers or extended abstracts published in any means following a peer review) have been produced by users as a direct result of access to E-RIHS services (explicitly mentioning E-RIHS within the paper or comprising co-authorship)?

NOTE 1: New providers (less than two years as part of E-RIHS) do not need to complete this question.

NOTE 2: This question is only relevant for managed services where access is dependent on a formal application (not an 'available' DIGILAB service).

Project Acronym	Publication details	Doi/URL	Is co-authorship user-provider comprised?

On consideration of the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), how does the facility regard the value and impact of their research outputs using qualitative indicators such as rigour, collaboration, innovation, and influence on practice or policy?

NOTE: Examples of evidence: following rigorous writing practices like citing primary literature instead of review papers, publishing in open access journals, partnering with international colleagues on projects, undertaking research in consultation with stakeholders within the community, developing new methods or techniques, commercialising academic research, participating in public engagement activities, advising non-profit or governmental organisations, contributing to the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals.

6. WIDER IMPACT

What **dissemination events** did the research group organise (in which E-RIHS is involved), nationally or internationally, during the previous year? What was the associated participant satisfaction rating (%) for each event?

NOTE: If more space is needed, create additional rows within the table.

Dissemination events organised by research group	Satisfaction rating (%)

Did your research group participate in any national or international **dissemination events** in the last 12 months? Please list these below.

What **educational events** did the research group organise (in which E-RIHS is involved), nationally or internationally, during the previous year? What was the associated participant satisfaction rating (%) for each event?

NOTE: If more space is needed, create additional rows within the table.

Education events organised by research group	Satisfaction rating (%)

Did your research group participate in any national or international **education events** in the last 12 months?

7. DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE

In the last 12 months, what is the % of datasets related to service accesses that have been added to an E-RIHS listed repository relative to the number of accesses?

NOTE: (number of datasets / total number of services accessed)*100. Objective: Check that data produced as part of access to services is being uploaded to data repositories in a timely manner.

Do the services provided have an accessible DMP?

Does the DMP conform to the core E-RIHS standard and, if not, have variations from this been recorded?

Are users required to upload a reasonable data management plan, which stipulates embargoes and a planned E-RIHS listed repository?

NOTE: This question is only relevant for managed services where access is dependent on a formal application (not an 'available' DIGILAB service).

What is the % of datasets related to service accesses that have a complete data management package and can be considered a FAIR digital object?

NOTE 1: This question is only relevant for managed physical or digital services where access is dependent on a formal application (not an 'available' DIGILAB service).

NOTE 2: (datasets for which post access duties have been completed / total number of datasets)*100. Objective: Establish if data management plans are being followed and completed.

Digital services (DIGILAB)

NOTE: Only providers of E-RIHS DIGILAB services need to complete this section.

What is the % of users who access a service can still be found using the service one month on from initial access?

NOTE: (users still using service after one month/total number of users)*100. Objective: Establish how engaged users are with the services on offer within E-RIHS.

What % of users rate quality of 'available' DIGILAB services as higher than 4 out of 5?

NOTE 1: (users rating useability of services as 4 out of 5 or above / total number of users who have provided feedback)*100. Objective: Establish if users find DIGILAB services easy to use and accessible and flag issues.

NOTE 2: This question is not relevant for managed DIGILAB services where access is dependent on a formal application.

I.4 Recommendation Form for New Services

Annex I.5 is used by the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board, assisted by the Committee of National Node or an ad hoc committee, to prepare the recommendation report for evaluating proposed new services. The evaluation grid aligns with the key criteria outlined in the New Service Assessment Form (Annex I.2).

NOTE: Please indicate 'YES' if the proposal satisfies the criterion, or 'NO' if it does not. Add comments if necessary to explain your assessment.

Provider: National Node: Year of Submission: Title of New Services: Platform: <input type="checkbox"/> ARCHLAB <input type="checkbox"/> FIXLAB <input type="checkbox"/> MOLAB			
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSMENT	YES	NO	Comments if necessary
Value Proposition			
Facility and Equipment			
Personnel			
Service Quality			
RECOMMENDATION	PROVIDE REASONING		
Approval			
Approval with request for improvement or corrective actions			
Pending (proposal to postpone with request for improvement or corrective actions)			
Rejection			

Signature

[reviewer]

I confirm that the information provided is true and accurate to the best of my knowledge.

Date _____

Name _____

Signature (handwritten or digital) _____

I.5 Assessment Form for Existing Services

Form to be used by the quality representative or National Node Coordinator.

NOTE: Please tick either 'Satisfactory' or 'Unsatisfactory'; please add any comments as to why you have made this judgement.

Provider: National Node: Year:			
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSMENT	SATISFACTORY	UNSATISFACTORY	COMMENTS
Facilities and equipment			
Personnel			
Service quality and relevance			
Feedback from users			
Scientific and wider impact			
Digital access (if appropriate)			

If the National Node has identified any areas for improvement or corrective actions to be taken and necessary time frame that should be communicated with the provider, please detail these here.

Signature

[National Node Coordinator or NN quality representative]

I confirm that the information provided is true and accurate to the best of my knowledge.

Date _____

Name _____

Signature (handwritten or digital) _____

ANNEX II. E-RIHS ERIC ENDORSEMENT: REQUEST AND LETTER TEMPLATES

II.1 Request for a E-RIHS Letter of Endorsement: Templates

EXAMPLE 1

[Organization Name]
[Name Surname] – [Position/Title]
[Email Address]

Date: [Insert Date]

To: Director General of E-RIHS
Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS

Ref: Request for a Letter of Endorsement to be Issued to [organization] for [project/initiative]

CONTACT DETAILS
Contact person: Name Surname Position Affiliation e-mail: phone number:
CALL INFORMATION
Entity the proposed project will be submitted:
Call to which the proposed project will be submitted:
DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT PROPOSAL TO WHICH THE ENDORSEMENT LETTER IS ISSUED
Title of the project:
Abstract:
Keywords:
Coordinator:
List of partners:
IMPACT ON E-RIHS ERIC
OTHER COMMENTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I hereby declare that the data generated in the frame of the project will follow the FAIR principles. I hereby authorize the use of my personal data in accordance to the GDPR 679/16 "European regulation on the protection of personal data".

EXAMPLE 2

[Organization Name]

[Name Surname] – [Position/Title]

[Email Address]

Date: [Insert Date]

To: Director General of E-RIHS
Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS

Ref: Request for a Letter of Endorsement to be Issued to [organization] for [project/initiative]

[E-RIHS Letterhead or Logo]

Date: [Insert Date]

To Whom It May Concern,

Subject: Endorsement of [Project/Person/Organization Name]

Alignment with E-RIHS Mission:

The aim of *[Project Name]* is to [briefly describe the project's objective], which directly supports the advancement of E-RIHS's key goals of [mention specific goals such as innovation, research collaboration, scientific excellence, etc.]. In particular, this project will [explain how the project fits with the E-RIHS's scientific, ethical, or societal objectives].

Expected Outcomes and Impact:

- Scientific Contribution: [Describe the expected scientific impact or contribution of the project, mentioning how it supports innovation or advances current knowledge in your field.]
- Societal or Practical Benefits: [Explain the broader impact of the project on society, industry, healthcare, or environmental sustainability.]

We kindly request your endorsement in the form of [describe the type of endorsement you are seeking: a formal letter, branding authorization, public announcement, etc.]. Such support from E-RIHS would significantly enhance our project's credibility, visibility, and outreach, helping us to achieve greater scientific and societal impact.

Upon endorsement, we are committed to providing periodic updates on the project's progress and ensuring that all outputs align with E-RIHS's standards and values. We confirm that the data generated in the frame of the project will follow the FAIR principles. We are happy to comply with any additional requirements or guidelines needed to maintain this collaboration.

Thank you for considering our request. We look forward to the opportunity to collaborate with E-RIHS and contribute to advancing research in [relevant field].

Sincerely,

II.2 E-RIHS Letter of Endorsement: Template

[E-RIHS Letterhead or Logo]

Date: [Insert Date]

To Whom It May Concern,

Subject: Endorsement of [Project/Person/Organization Name]

Dear [Recipient's Name or "Sir/Madam"],

On behalf of E-RIHS, I am pleased to express our endorsement of [Project/Person/Organization Name]. As a distributed research infrastructure dedicated to advancing scientific collaboration in the field of heritage science, we recognize the exceptional value that [Project/Person/Organization Name] brings to [relevant field/ community].

[Provide a brief overview of the project, person, or organization you are endorsing, highlighting their achievements, contributions, and alignment with E-RIHS's goals and values.]

We believe that [Project/Person/Organization Name] exemplifies the highest standards of [relevant field/quality/innovation], and their work aligns with our mission to [insert relevant E-RIHS mission or vision statement]. Therefore, we strongly support [his/her/their/its] efforts and are confident in [his/her/their/its] continued success.

We look forward to collaborations and are excited about the potential impact of [Project/Person/Organization Name]'s work within the [community/field].

Please feel free to contact us at [contact information] if you require any further information or clarification.

Sincerely,

E-RIHS Director General

ANNEX III. E-RIHS DIGITAL SERVICES QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Annex III is derived from the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase deliverable D2.2 *Quality Manual and KPIs* (Mimoso et al., 2020) and is included here for completeness. Further improvements may result from collaboration with initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). These initiatives can enhance the quality assessment of E-RIHS data by providing frameworks for interoperability, FAIR data principles, and domain-specific tools. EOSC offers standards for trustworthiness, preservation, and accessibility, while ECCCH focuses on facilitating the integration of cultural heritage datasets, supporting advanced data processing tools, and ensuring alignment with ethical and scientific priorities specific to the heritage domain. This collaboration can strengthen E-RIHS's capacity to deliver high-quality, reusable data for research in heritage science.

Annex III outlines a tentative process for evaluating whether to accept or reject: (a) datasets proposed for registration in the DIGILAB registry (henceforth, *data provision services*) and (b) data processing tools proposed for inclusion in the DIGILAB portfolio (henceforth, *tool services*). The steps and procedures are aligned with the specifications detailed in the main document, the E-RIHS Quality Policy.

Publicly available datasets, such as those published within an Open Data framework, may also be considered for inclusion. For tool services, software tools in the public domain, Open Source, freely available, or commercial ones may also be eligible.

Digital access differs from physical access, as it has in practice no limitation on the number of users accessing the service. Access can also be repeated as necessary, consuming data and using data services with no limitation or cost increase beyond the ones for storage and management. Furthermore, digital services have their own specific requirements about quality and use, summarized below with the related indicators. In any case, offering access to datasets or tool services implies an indirect endorsement by E-RIHS, so they should be carefully verified before being incorporated in the E-RIHS digital access offer.

Defining quality criteria at the earliest opportunity is crucial to start (and test) the operations of DIGILAB, as this is in practice a brand-new facility offered to the research community.

III.1 Step 1: Assessment of Data or Tool Provider

This part is identical to the candidate provider assessment used for physical access services. In the case of a recurring or regular provision of different data/services this step may be omitted.

If there is no provider, it must be however specified who oversees maintaining, updating, and curating the data or supporting the service, and how these activities are planned to be carried out. The assessment will be applied to such a substitute provider.

III.2 Step 2: Evaluation of Services Offered

The procedure is like the general one outlined for all physical access services, only differing because there is no “Access Selection” subsection, and the “Service Quality and Relevance” subsection are replaced by the following.

III.2.1 TOOL SERVICES

This kind of services consists in the on-line provision of tools, for example image processing or visualization tools, to process existing datasets made available through DIGILAB or datasets provided by the user for processing.

Service quality and relevance

General features

- Is the service innovative and useful for E-RIHS purposes?
- Does service use require registration?
- Are there general conditions/restrictions to use the service (e.g. a CC-NC license)?
- Is the service use restricted to a particular category of users (e.g. registered professionals)?
- Is the service software provided under an open licensing scheme (e.g. BSD, GPL, etc.)?
- Is the service suitable to work in a cloud environment such as the EOSC?
- Does the service apply/use/require data standards?

Service management and documentation

- Are the service and its software well documented?
- Is such documentation available to users?
- Are on-line help and user manual available to users?
- Is result interpretation clearly explained, when necessary?

User support

- Is a support service available for non-expert users?
- Are bug reporting and commenting by users implemented?

Maintenance and sustainability

- Is there a maintenance plan for the service?
- Is there a sustainability plan for the service?

Data management

- Can results obtained using the tool be saved and incorporated in the DIGILAB repository, made available for later use, or stored for re-use by other researchers?
- Is a data management policy implemented for the results obtained using the tool, including a Data Management Plan compliant with the E-RIHS standards?

III.2.2 DATA PROVISION SERVICES

This case consists in the provision of external datasets to E-RIHS (i.e. generated outside of E-RIHS activities) for incorporation in DIGILAB; for example, this may include the provision of digital reference collections, results of analyses, reports of conservation work, and so on. The incorporation

in DIGILAB may be *actual*, through the transfer of such datasets to a DIGILAB-controlled repository, managed by E-RIHS; or *virtual*, by enabling access through DIGILAB to data stored with the data provider. The assessment consists in the evaluation of the following aspects.

(Only for datasets stored with the data provider)

- Is the repository appropriately curated?
- Does the repository comply with standard repository trustworthiness conditions (e.g. DSA, ISO 16363 [A02.01], DIN 31644 [A02.02])?
- Is a long-term preservation plan existing and appropriate?

(Only for datasets deposited at the E-RIHS repository)

- Which is the data ingestion mechanism?
- Is it compliant with established standards (e.g. OAI-PMH)?
- Which are the frequency and the mechanism planned for updates (if applicable)?

(For all datasets, both those managed by the data provider and those deposited with ERIHS)

- Are the data relevant for E-RIHS?
- Are there plans for regular data update and curation?
- Is a Data Management Plan required for data deposit by creators?
- Is such Data Management Plan compliant with E-RIHS requirements?
- Is the contributed dataset well documented as concerns data trustworthiness (e.g. who produced the data, for which purpose, in which conditions, using which protocol, and so on)?
- Are such provenance metadata provided in the DMP or in another document?
- Does access to data require registration?
- Are there general conditions for/restrictions to data re-use (e.g. a CC-NC license)?
- Is data access and re-use restricted to a particular category of users (e.g. registered professionals)?
- Are data provided under an open licensing scheme (e.g. CC0, BSD, GPL, etc.)?
- Does the dataset use/require data standards?

III.3 Step 3: Peer Review

Assessing and evaluating this aspect has in general less importance than in the general case. Interesting data and useful services may be provided, for example, by heritage management institutions with little scientific activity, by researchers operating in different domains or by software research unrelated to cultural heritage. So, this aspect in the main document on the quality policy will be considered as informative only.

ANNEX IV. KPI AND DATASHEETS

IV.1 Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are values that may be objectively measured allowing an unbiased appraisal of operational effectiveness. This annex is dedicated to outlining the set of KPIs that align with the specific objectives of E-RIHS to fulfil RACER criteria: Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor and Robust.

Adhering to the ESFRI Working Group on the monitoring of research infrastructures performance December of 2019 and recommendations of the 2016 ESFRI Projects monitoring exercise to *better describe E-RIHS indicators* delivered in 2021, a set of flexible Key Performance Indicators have been developed. Based tightly on experiences gathered in former European projects by the E-RIHS consortium, the monitoring of access provision, education, and training, has been implemented and tested. The base set of KPIs foreseeing the infrastructure commencing its operations has been supplemented with additional ESFRI categories that should necessarily be integrated into E-RIHS ERIC. These include and are not limited to categories for- provision of scientific advice; Policy related activities; optimizing management- Revenues and Facilitating economic activities-income from commercial activities. Each KPI which follows has been accompanied by its narrative with definition, method of calculation, and other information concerning its applicability.

The set KPIs are to be used for the self-assessment of all services provided and of the productivity of research and support to research at the National Node level to be reported annually to the Central Hub. Non-compliance with targets should induce providers to review their internal procedures, introduce corrections and generally aim at improving their performance towards users and the providers in general. KPIs will also be considered (albeit not singly) for the purpose of periodic assessments of E-RIHS.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS	
Number	Indicator
FINANCES AND DEVELOPMENT	
1.	Revenue
2.	Number of Members in E-RIHS
ECONOMIC ACTIVITES	
3.	Income from commercial activities and number of entities paying for service
4.	Share of users and publications associated with industry
USER ACCESS	
5.	Number of user requests for access
6.	Retention of Access Users
7.	Access demand
8.	Number of users served (and share per EU, non-EU country)
9.	Number of Access provisions
10.	Access quality feedback
11.	Number of publications (open access and share per country)

12.	Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
HS ACADEMY	
13.	Number of participants in dissemination and education events
14.	Number of hours of dissemination events
15.	Number of master and PhD students using E-RIHS
16.	Training of people who are not E-RIHS staff
17.	Educational/training quality feedback
DATA MANAGEMENT AND DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	
18.	Number of available datasets (public and restricted)
19.	Number of datasets used externally
COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH	
20.	Outreach through printed, broadcast and web-based media
21.	Outreach via the E-RIHS's own web and social media activities
22.	Engagement achieved by direct contact (events)
PROVISION OF SCIENTIFIC ADVICE	
23.	Participation by RIs in policy related activities
24.	Citations in policy related publications

IV.2 Data sheets with short narratives

Data sheets for each of the 24 KPIs are organised in relation to E-RIHS and ESFRI objectives. Whilst the objectives are relevant for E-RIHS, some of the proposed KPIs cannot, at the time of writing, be fully implemented until steady state operational E-RIHS ERIC is achieved. Some further adaptation is fully expected to be needed for a certain KPI to be fully applicable to the needs of the RI. A short narrative for each KPI follows, putting it in its specific context.

This may be a general reference for consultation, subject to further tailoring in E-RIHS.

IV.1.1 FINANCES AND DEVELOPMENT

Revenue

ESFRI Objective	Optimizing Management
Number	1
Indicator	Revenues
Definition(s)	Sources of revenue and their respective contributions to investments and operational costs
Rationale	Indicator demonstrates the funding available for various activities. Changes over the years indicate development stages of E-RIHS regarding construction, upgrades and decommissioning – depending on the point in the lifecycle of the RI - and the level of operations, which in turn provides an indication of the sustainability of the RI
Who is providing this information	Central Hub accounting, inputs from national hubs
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	The indicator is calculated by adding the following revenue categories - Financial and in-kind contributions received from members - Financial and in-kind contributions received by third parties - Financial and in-kind contributions related to project externally funded

	- Commercial revenues - Other revenues All these items are accounted according to the accounting standards adopted by the institution (accrual criteria vs financial criteria)
Unit of measure	Amount in national currency; nature of the revenue
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	A true assessment seems to require information on target and actual values, as well as reflections on alternative solutions (if there are funding deficits).
E-RIHS PID	

Number of Members in E-RIHS

ESFRI Objective	Enhancing collaboration in Europe Facilitating international cooperation
Number	2
Indicator	Number of Members in E-RIHS
Definition(s)	Number of organisations/countries with a formal engagement (e.g. members, associated members or observers, bound by legal agreement or MoU), who are based in an ESFRI or non ESFRI member country.
Rationale	Indicator provides a measure of the extent to which the RI may play a role to: help coordinate and facilitate integration at European and international level; to promote common standards, tools and practice; to expand the catalogue of activities available at RIs to new beneficiaries/members or provider countries
Data/information needs and resources	Data collected by the Central Hub
Who is providing this information	Provided by the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Count number of Members according to each type of formal engagement, including the country hosting the RI. The nature of the engagement should be classified by type (where relevant): - Members - Associated members - Observers
Unit of measure	Number
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Increase numbers of formal engagement yearly Year 1: +1; year 2....
E-RIHS PID	

IV.1.2 ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES

Income from commercial activities and number of entities paying for service

ESFRI Objective	Facilitating Economic Activities
Number	3
Indicator	Income from commercial activities and number of entities paying for service

Definition(s)	Share of revenue from the RI's economic activities (sale of services, access provision) reported in the in the annual accounts
Rationale	Indicator for the level of commercial activity in relation to the overall level of operation of E-RIHS
Who is providing this information	Accounting at the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Sum of the revenues from E-RIHS economic activities (sale of services and goods; access provision from users, which are not funded), and the number of entities
Unit of measure	Share of total revenue in %; the number of entities paying;
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Year 1-2 2%; Year 3 ca. 5% Ca. 10% total revenue at steady state operations
E-RIHS PID	

Share of users and publications associated with industry

ESFRI Objective	Facilitating Economic Activities
Number	4
Indicator	Share of users and publications associated with industry
Definition(s)	As defined in KPI 8, KPI 11
Rationale	Indicator of the extent to which scientists from industry, E-RIHS and possibly also one or more universities collaborate and exchange knowledge.
Who is providing this information	As defined in KPI 8, KPI 11
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	As defined in KPI 8, KPI 11
Unit of measure	% and number
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	N.b it might not be able to report on the share of non-proprietary industrial users.
E-RIHS PID	

IV.1.3 USER ACCESS TO E-RIHS

Number of user requests for access

ESFRI Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	5
Indicator	Number of user requests for access
Definition(s)	For access to: physical platforms (ARCHLAB/FIXLAB/MOLAB): number of user requests submitted for access in every single or multi-facility application. The number of application submissions is also recorded digital services: number of users requests submitted for DIGILAB services (terms of access under definition)
Rationale	Indicator of the attractiveness of E-RIHS- in terms of visibility and offer of services

Data/information needs and resources	A tracking/recording system for physical platforms: from the internal dashboard. The disciplines/backgrounds of users is also tracked herein. digital services: TBD
Who is providing this information	physical platforms: Central Hub from the internal dashboard digital services: TBD
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Requests in E-RIHS come from registered users physical platforms: Record and report the number of users involved in each application for access at each call. Total users are given on multiplication by the number of facilities requested in each individual application. This can be segregated by platform, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB. Digital services: the number of specific requests per single user submitted can be reported
Unit of measure	Number
Frequency of measurement	Following each call for physical platforms (biannually) Annually for digital services
Additional observations	The number of users is given by the total number of users in the user group represented in every submitted application form.
Target	For steady state operations, arrive to 600 users per year to physical platforms plus considerations for DIGILAB once constructed. Application no. >100 yearly
E-RIHS PID	

Retention of Access users

E-RIHS Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	6
Indicator	Retention of Access users
Definition(s)	The number of application submissions from experienced user group leaders and % of new user group leaders
Rationale	Indicator of the continued attractiveness of E-RIHS- in terms of visibility and offer of services to new users and communities
Data/information needs and resources	A tracking/recording system for physical platforms: from the internal dashboard. Cross check of users to previous calls/ newly registered with community affiliation digital services: through number of formal requests by registered users- TBD
Who is providing this information	physical platforms: Central Hub from the internal dashboard digital services: TBD
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Requests in E-RIHS come from registered users physical platforms: Record and report the number of user group leaders- new, experienced involved in each application for access at each call. This can be segregated by platform, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB. Digital services: the number of specific requests per single new/experienced user submitted can be reported Subgroup- KPI 15- users at early stage of career- PhD or masters students
Unit of measure	Number and % with map of community affiliation
Frequency of measurement	Following each call for physical platforms (biannually) Annually for digital services

Additional observations	The number of users is given by the total number of users in the user group represented in every submitted application form.
Target	All users are considered “new” on beginning of operations. Numbers will grow as E-RIHS does
E-RIHS PID	

Access Demand

E-RIHS Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	7
Indicator	Access demand
Definition(s)	For each service constituting the physical platforms (ARCHLAB/FIXLAB/MOLAB), the percentage of accesses requested over the available slots of access.
Rationale	Verification of demand and supply of all services. Indication of over/under subscription for each service, that there is sufficient demand to and available slots for each service offered. Furthermore, that the offer of access is sufficient to attract a high inflow of researchers from disciplines in HS whilst maintaining competitive nature to the call for scientific excellence
Data/information needs and resources	Number of slots for each service per year and number of requests per service per call must be captured for input into a tracking system. -The disciplines of user group projects is also mapped within the same system.
Who is providing this information	Data collected through the dashboard and provided by the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	(Access requested/Available access slots per service) x100
Unit of measure	Percentage
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Beyond 100% yearly for all platforms
E-RIHS PID	

Number of users served (and share per EU, non-EU country)

ESFRI Objectives	Enabling scientific excellence Enhancing collaboration in Europe Facilitating international cooperation
Number	8
Indicator	Number of users served (and share per EU, non-EU country)
Definition(s)	For access to: physical platforms (ARCHLAB/FIXLAB/MOLAB): total number of users served from granted proposals. Numbers can be given per platform digital services: number of user requests resulting in provisions of service. Number of users served are also associated for EU and non-EU country in each year. Such indicators provide a measure of the extent to which E-RIHS may play a role to facilitate and optimise the use of pan-European facilities and to develop a Pan-European user community; increase the number of new users(experiments/projects) Also an indicator of the relevance/attractiveness of the RI internationally

Rationale	Indicator to measure the size of the community served per country and efficiency of operations.
Data/information needs and resources	Number of users for each service in each granted application per year must be captured for input into a tracking system for physical platforms: from the internal dashboard in accordance with accepted number of proposals digital services: TBD
Who is providing this information	physical platforms: Central Hub from the internal dashboard digital services: TBD
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	For accepted Applications /Requests in E-RIHS physical platforms: Record and report the number of users served for access and share per country. This can be segregated by platform, MOLAB, ARCHLAB, FIXLAB. Digital services: the number of users who have downloaded/ used services provided through DIGILAB is recorded and reported
Unit of measure	Number and % per country
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Initial operations- 300 users; to increase to 650 on steady operations
E-RIHS PID	

Number of access provisions

ESFRI Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	9
Indicator	Number of access provisions
Definition(s)	What is the total number of physical accesses delivered compared to the number of accesses currently planned but still to be delivered for each calendar year.
Rationale	Verify the effective carrying out of access for each providing service yearly
Data/information needs and resources	Number of slots indicated for each service per year and number of accesses carried out for that service per year must be captured for input into a tracking system
Who is providing this information	For physical platforms: provided by the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Number of accesses provided and (Accesses provided / Accesses planned) x100
Unit of measure	Number and %
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	100% for the previous year
E-RIHS PID	

Access Quality feedback

E-RIHS Objective	User feedback to physical and digital services
Number	10
Indicator	Access quality feedback

Definition(s)	Based on the E-RIHS satisfaction survey: what % of service accesses were rated higher than 8 (out of 10) by users.
Rationale	Appraise the quality of the service from the perspective of users. Designed to gather feedback at each step of the E-RIHS “user experience” - from first contact, application submission, granted application, access organization, execution, fulfilment of objectives and post access.
Data/information needs and resources	To be determined: The user satisfaction survey should be automatically sent to the physical and digital users on access completion as implemented through the dashboard wordpress. The resulting statistics will be held by survey monkey or similar.
Who is providing this information	Feedback will be provided by the Central Hub and communicated to providers via National Nodes.
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Online automatic statistics generated-To be determined
Unit of measure	Percentage
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Target: KPI > 80% after an initial probation period of 12 months.
E-RIHS PID	

Number of publications

ESFRI Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	11
Indicator	Number of publications (open access and share per country)
Definition(s)	How many publications yearly (full papers or extended abstracts published in any means following a peer review) have been produced by users as a direct result of access to E-RIHS services (explicitly mentioning E-RIHS within the paper or comprising co-authorship). Can be reported according to service. What percentage of these have been published in open access
Rationale	Verify the impact of E-RIHS in the heritage science research landscape through the dissemination of data and knowledge. Related primarily to the quantity of science enabled and in a secondary fashion to the quality of the science enabled
Data/information needs and resources	Much of the published output will be captured using commercial databases such as WoS and Scopus which contain mainly articles published in peer reviewed journals. However, to widen the field of capture this requires the providers from National Nodes and oblige users to signal the information (periodic assessment)- including proceedings papers, book chapters, books and technical reports.
Who is providing this information	Signalled by Service provider of all National Nodes in the periodic assessment
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	New providers (less than two years as part of E-RIHS) do not need to complete this question. This question is only relevant for managed services where access is dependent on a formal application (not an ‘available’ DIGILAB service). 1. Collect the publications based on the research performed using facilities/resources of E-RIHS resorting to the variety of means outlined above. 2. Count and calculate percentage in open access
Unit of measure	Number and %

Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Yearly publications should aim to reflect the quantity of science enabled 1:1 ratio of publication vs accepted application through competitive calls >40% in open access, to increase yearly
E-RIHS PID	

Percentage of top (10%) cited publications

ESFRI Objective	Enabling scientific excellence
Number	12
Indicator	Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
Definition(s)	Percentage of publications based on research performed using facilities/resources of E-RIHS that, compared with the publications in the same field and in the same year, belong to the top 10% most frequently cited.
Rationale	Indicator of the quality/impact of science enabled.
Data/information needs and resources	Access to commercial citation databases WoS or Scopus
Who is providing this information	Signalled by Service provider of all National Nodes in the periodic assessment
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define the publication dates and determine the number of papers published and included in WoS or Scopus. 2. Define the citation window and retrieve the number of citations. 3. Determine the WoS or Scopus subject category. 4. Retrieve the normalization factors. 6. Calculate the field/year/type of publication normalized citation score. 7. Calculate (or retrieve) the top 10% boundaries. 8. Calculate the percentage of publications in the top10%
Unit of measure	Percentage
Frequency of measurement	Biannually, with rolling publication dates. E.g. In 2020, the publications 2015-2018 In 2022, the publications 2017-2019
Target	The indicator is not suitable for very young RIs. A period of 4 to 5 years after publication is needed to have enough citation data.
E-RIHS PID	

IV.14 HS ACADEMY

Number of participants in dissemination and education events

ESFRI Objective	Delivery of education and training
Number	13
Indicator	Number of participants in dissemination and education events
Definition(s)	Yearly no. attendees in dissemination events (webinars, lectures, user meetings, conferences etc). Yearly number of attendees in education events (Training camps and summer schools).
Rationale	Indicator of the reach and engagement that E-RIHS commands with which it is able to attract participants to attend dissemination and training

	events. Number of attendees must be captured for each event and recorded for later input into tracking system.
Who is providing this information	Provided by all providers organising events to the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	1. Collate information on participation at educational events throughout the year. 2. Add up total number of participants across the year. 3. Analyse participants broken down by level (national, international) or by field.
Unit of measure	Number
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be adequately determined: Previous data include: 1000 yearly for dissemination events (2021-2024) 84 yearly for education events (2021-23)
E-RIHS PID	

Number of hours of dissemination events

ESFRI Objective	Delivery of education and training
Number	14
Indicator	Number of hours of dissemination events
Definitions(s)	Yearly no. of hours offered by E-RIHS to dissemination events- webinars, lectures. Conferences etc Current topics in HS
Rationale	Indicator of how much accessible training E-RIHS is able to offer the heritage science community. Assumes a 'simple' correspondence between the hours provided in face-to-face or on-line training and the extent of that training (i.e. all hours regarded as equally valuable or effective) and that this can be captured effectively.
Who is providing this information	Provided by all providers organising events and communicated to the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	1. Collate information on dissemination events throughout the year. 2. Add up total number of hours across the year.
Unit of measure	Number of hours
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be adequately determined: Previous data include: 9 hours yearly for dissemination events (2021-2024)
E-RIHS PID	

Number of master and PhD students using E-RIHS

ESFRI Objective	Delivery of education and training
Number	15
Indicator	Number of master and PhD students using E-RIHS

Definitions(s)	Number of master and PhD students who have performed some of their studies at or using the services of the RI in a particular year regardless of whether they are funded/hosted by the RI or access it as a user
Rationale	Indicator of the extent of the education and training of the external academic community, comprising both experienced and potential users. Each student is given the same weight regardless of importance of RI with regard to training opportunities (registered participants)
Who is providing this information	Check for PhD/Master students Access to physical facilities- the E-RIHS dashboard can check through the Central Hub. Provided by all providers for organized events and communicated to the Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Add up total number of students participating in access or events across the year. Can be corrected for multiple accesses in any one year to determine the unique number of people in this category in any one year
Unit of measure	Number
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be determined -not before collected
E-RIHS PID	

Training of people who are not E-RIHS Staff

ESFRI Objective	Delivery of education and training
Number	16
Indicator	Training of people who are not E-RIHS staff
Definitions(s)	The total number of person hours for which people external to the RI have made use of training opportunities provided by the RI, through both real (e.g. face to face) events and on-line services (registered participants)
Rationale	Education and training of the external academic community. Assumes a 'simple' correspondence between the hours provided in face-to-face or on-line training and the extent of that training (i.e. all hours regarded as equally valuable or effective) and that this can be captured effectively.
Who is providing this information	Recording of affiliations of all participants to training events in E-RIHS. By each National Node and sent yearly to Central Hub for calculation
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Add up total number of participant hours by non E-RIHS staff in training events across the year.
Unit of measure	Person hours
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be determined -not before collected
E-RIHS PID	

Educational and Training Quality feedback

E-RIHS Objective	User feedback
Number	17
Indicator	Educational and Training quality feedback
Definition(s)	What educational events were organised, nationally or internationally, during the previous year. What was the associated participant satisfaction rating (%) for each event.
Rationale	Appraises the quality of the event and its organisation from the perspective of participants.
Data/information needs and resources	To be determined- the event satisfaction survey should be automatically sent to registered participants as implemented through the dashboard wordpress. The resulting statistics will be held by survey monkey or similar
Who is providing this information	Feedback will be provided by the Central Hub or providers (depending on whether the event was organised centrally or not).
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	To be determined-Online automatic statistics generated
Unit of measure	Percentage
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Target: KPI > 80%
E-RIHS PID	

IV.1.5 DATA MANAGEMENT AND DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE**Number of FAIR datasets available (public and restricted)**

ESFRI Objective	Optimizing data use
Number	18
Indicator	Number of FAIR datasets available (public and restricted)
Definition(s)	Number of datasets related to all service accesses- both public and restricted. Number of public datasets that are FAIR and have been added to an E-RIHS listed repository relative to access. * restricted datasets may not be available The percentage of datasets related to service accesses that have a complete data management package and can be considered a FAIR digital object.
Rationale	Indicator of the extent to which the data that E-RIHS produces is made FAIR and available for people possibly in the same scientific domain, in other scientific domains or even by the general public.
Data/information needs and resources	Check that data produced as part of access to services is being uploaded to data repositories in a timely manner. Establishes if data management plans are being followed and completed. This information should be recorded
Who is providing this information	input from National Nodes passed to Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	For the physical services- each access should likely produce a dataset, percentage with FAIR digital status
Unit of measure	Number and %
Frequency of measurement	Annually

Target	To be determined each access should produce a dataset, year 1 >80% FAIR, year 3 100%
E-RIHS PID	

Number of datasets used externally

ESFRI Objective	Optimizing data use
Number	19
Indicator	Number of datasets used externally
Definition(s)	Number of data sets produced as a consequence of access to the RI that are subsequently accessed by other users
Rationale	Indicator of the extent to which the data that E-RIHS produces/makes available is regarded as useful by people who could be in the same scientific domain, in other scientific domains or even by the general public. Its use thus provides some indicator of the wider significance of the data
Data/information needs and resources	Number of downloads of datasets from the E-RIHS repository and number of resulting publications
Who is providing this information	TBD- Central Hub with input from National Nodes
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Possibly tracking, to be determined
Unit of measure	Number of datasets, number of resulting publications of downloaded datasets (from specific “requests” to digital services)
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be determined, may need refinement after a period of test usage
E-RIHS PID	

IV.1.6 COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH

Outreach through printed, broadcast and web-based media

ESFRI Objective	Outreach to the public
Number	20
Indicator	Outreach through printed, broadcast and web-based media
Definition(s)	Impact of press and communication actions in raising awareness of RI mission, activities and societal relevance of results
Rationale	Measurement of result of the E-RIHS activity in terms of awareness and understanding within the general public and policy circles. It is assumed that the E-RIHS has in place a public relations/media strategy and at least one member of staff working in this field to ensure reporting and monitoring occurs.
Data/information needs and resources	The information required concerns compiling a record of mentions of the RI in different media (press, TV, radio, etc.) – this may include interviews of RI management or researchers, articles/reporting based on press releases, etc.
Who is providing this information	The information should be gathered by the communications officer of E-RIHS

Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	Number of times E-RIHS is mentioned in press articles, radio or TV broadcasts or web-based media not-related to E-RIHS. Multiple mentions within one media report is counted as one.
Unit of measure	Number
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Steady increase from initial operations
E-RIHS PID	

Outreach via E-RIHS’s own web and social media activities

ESFRI Objective	Outreach to the public
Number	21
Indicator	Outreach via E-RIHS’s own web and social media activities
Definition(s)	Website popularity and level of social media engagement: Web (e.g. Google analytics) analytics and social media analytic tools (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube, Flickr, Facebook, etc.)
Rationale	E-RIHS presence and engagement via web and social media activities, It is assumed that the RI has in place a social media strategy and at least one member of staff is assigned responsibility for managing social media and analysing impact
Data/information needs and resources	Data is reported as per social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube, Flickr, Facebook, etc.)
Who is providing this information	-Communications officer of E-RIHS for main E-RIHS ERIC website. -Supplemented by Details collected biannually from the national hubs individual websites and passed to HQ. Data collected
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	For web sites standard indicators include: Users, New Users, Page views, Unique page views, Avg. session duration, etc. For social media, standard indicators include profile visits, total number and number of new followers (per period), mentions and interactions, etc.
Unit of measure	Numbers
Frequency of measurement	Biannually
Target	Steady increase from initial operations -Build on previous data: Yearly no. of website accesses- 59K (2022-23) to 68K (2023-24) -average duration of single website access 01:36 mins -social media insight 2022-24 Twitter 6.9K followers; you-tube 7.9K views; Facebook 7.6K post engagement; LinkedIn 100K page reach
E-RIHS PID	

Engagement achieved by direct contact

ESFRI Objective	Outreach to the public
Number	22
Indicator	Engagement achieved by direct contact
Definition(s)	Outreach by public relations/direct contact with specific target groups: organisation of (events for industry, government sector etc.) or participation at events organised by third parties; and visitors to the RI

Rationale	Provides a measure of the impact of E-RIHS in terms of raising public awareness and understanding of research in the fields in which the RI operates. The RI intends to track visitors, attendees at any events organised by the RI and participation of staff at external events, etc.
Data/information needs and resources	Tracking of numbers of visitors, attendees at industry events organised by the RI and participation of staff at external events, etc.
Who is providing this information	- Central Hub staff -National hubs for individual member states and staff therein
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	The indicators tracked include - number of visitors, - participants of the events and - events organised, number and hours (reported to a minimum 0.25 days)
Unit of measure	Number of visitors/participants, number and hours of events
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Steady increase from initial operations
E-RIHS PID	

IV.1.7 PROVISION OF SCIENTIFIC ADVICE

Participation of E-RIHS in policy related activities

ESFRI Objective	Provision of Scientific advise
Number	23
Indicator	Participation of E-RIHS in policy related activities
Definition(s)	Number of participations, reimbursed by the organisers, in policy related working groups, committees & advisory boards. In the case of working groups, etc, organised by intergovernmental organisations, the invitation suffices.
Rationale	Indicator of the extent to which E-RIHS is deemed as relevant by policy makers. Both for science policy and for addressing societal challenges. RIs may enable scientific developments within a particular challenge and may contribute to developments of policies such as those contributing to development of ERA, ESFRI, etc. Invitations of the staff linked to the RI, with the affiliation of the RI acknowledged, to participate in working groups, committees and advisory boards (contributing to the SDG or other societal challenges as well as to the European Research Area or dedicated to industry), reflect the policy relevance of a certain RI. Working groups, committees and advisory boards should be external to the RI and should have an international composition, or advise an international or national body (e.g. UN entities, ministries, agencies). In the case of multiple meetings linked to one e.g. advisory group, every attendance counts as a participation
Data/information needs and resources	Track of information by National Nodes where applicable and communication to Central Hub
Who is providing this information	Central Hub
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	1. Collate information on participation to and contributions by RI staff to policy events, relevant working groups, etc. 2. Presentations, working papers, reports etc. to which the RI has contributed can be collated and shared via dedicated space on the RI website or via ResearchGate, etc. 3.

	Analyse contributions broken down by level (Global, European, national, etc.) or by theme
Unit of measure	Number of invitations/contributions (working notes, joint reports, etc.)
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	To be determined
E-RIHS PID	

Citations in policy related publications

ESFRI Objective	Provision of Scientific advise
Number	23
Indicator	Citations in policy related publications
Definition(s)	Number of times the RI or its projects are cited in policy related publications
Rationale	Indicator of the extent to which the RI and the research that results from it is involved in influencing policy.
Data/information needs and resources	The information requires assigning responsibility for tracking citations to a dedicated member of staff, this could be the strategy director or similar function.
Who is providing this information	Central Hub based on monitoring European and national policy developments in their field of science, etc
Detailed methodology for indicator calculation	1. Collect the citations – this can be done using (social) media monitoring (see the related KPI on outreach) or by a dedicated monitoring of key government departments/agencies with which the RI works or interacts. Policy publications are publications dedicated to policy makers (governments, agencies, etc). Scientific publications and publications for the general public do not count in this category. 2. Several citations related to the same achievement in one document count as one citation. 3. Aggregate and present visualisations of the data (trend over time, etc).
Unit of measure	Number of citations
Frequency of measurement	Annually
Target	Requires refinement after a period of test usage
E-RIHS PID	

ANNEX V. EXAMPLES OF E-RIHS SATISFACTION FEEDBACK FORMS

Satisfaction and feedback forms are essential tools for ensuring the quality and effectiveness of the access and training services provided by E-RIHS. These forms allow users to share their experiences, assess the quality of the services, and suggest improvements. The feedback helps the infrastructure continuously improve its offerings, address user needs, and maintain high standards of performance and user satisfaction.

To maximize the benefit of these forms, which follow are examples that can be tailored, they should be filled out after each service or training session. Regular completion ensures that feedback remains timely and relevant, allowing E-RIHS to make data-driven decisions for enhancing future services and training opportunities.

V.1 Access Services

ACCESS USER SATISFACTION SURVEY

We greatly value the opinion of
IPERION HS Transnational access (TNA) Users

By taking a few minutes to fill out this survey, you can help the platforms to continue to improve their access provision. We are interested in your honest opinion. Your survey responses are voluntary. Thank you for your time.
(Please rate from 1=very poor to 10=Excellent)

1. Access to platform: (dropdown menu- ARCHLAB; FIXLAB; MOLAB)
2. User Project Acronym: -----
3. The publicity made by the IPERION HS project concerning the available services and calls for access to the platforms
1-10
4. Practical information on how to apply as well as the scientific and technical support given by the User helpdesk
1-10
5. Communication with provider/s prior to the access visit in the framework of its organization
1-10
6. Interaction and collaboration with the provider/s during the access visit
1-10
7. Added value of the results obtained for the advancement of your research
1-10
8. Overall fulfillment of expectations
1-10
9. You are kindly invited to provide suggestions enabling an improvement of our services or any comment.

V.2 Training

TRAINING SCHOOL SATISFACTION SURVEY

E-RIHS.mt Pilot Training School – Participant Satisfaction Survey

General	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Information was relevant professionally	<input type="radio"/>				
Course content met my expectations	<input type="radio"/>				
The programme was well placed	<input type="radio"/>				
I would be interested in attending a follow-up	<input type="radio"/>				
Participation and interaction were encouraged	<input type="radio"/>				
The overall quality of the Training School was high	<input type="radio"/>				
Day 2 - Archival Method					
Useful ideas, techniques and skills were presented	<input type="radio"/>				
My understanding on the topic was increased	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers were knowledgeable on the subject	<input type="radio"/>				
Delivered content was easy to follow	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers responded effectively to questions	<input type="radio"/>				
Day 3 - Archaeological Method					
Useful ideas, techniques and skills were presented	<input type="radio"/>				
My understanding on the topic was increased	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers were knowledgeable on the subject	<input type="radio"/>				
Delivered content was easy to follow	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers responded effectively to questions	<input type="radio"/>				
Day 4 - Scientific Method					
Useful ideas, techniques and skills were presented	<input type="radio"/>				
My understanding on the topic was increased	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers were knowledgeable on the subject	<input type="radio"/>				
Delivered content was easy to follow	<input type="radio"/>				
The trainers responded effectively to questions	<input type="radio"/>				

What did you most appreciate/enjoy/think was best about the training school? Any suggestions for improvement?

HS ACADEMY SATISFACTION SURVEY

HSAcademy

Current Topics

What do you think about the HS Academy lecture "Open and FAIR Science with a case study from the FAIR Phytoliths project"?

(Less than 2 minutes to give your feedback)

1. Which community do you identify yourself with?

Other (please specify)

2. Please rate your overall satisfaction with this lecture (1 being poor-10 being excellent)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3. Are there any topics you would like to see covered in future lectures?

4. Any further comments?

Participant Satisfaction Survey

By taking a few minutes to fill out this survey, your feedback can help the HS Academy to improve training activities. All response are confidential and will be analysed collectively with other participant responses. Thank you for your time.

Please rate from 0 = very poor to 10 = excellent.

1. How would you rate the overall quality of the training?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

2. How would you rate the practical information provided on how to apply to E-RIHS services and the application process?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3. How would you rate the organisation and timing of the training activities?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

4. How would you rate your satisfaction with the content of the theory sessions?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

5. How would you rate your satisfaction with the content of the practical sessions?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

6. Please provide further comments or suggestions below.

1st HS Academy Training Camp 2022 (1 HS-TC)
PARTICIPANT SATISFACTION SURVEY

By taking a few minutes to fill out this survey, your feedback can help the HS Academy improve training activities. All responses are confidential and will be analysed collectively with other participant responses. Thank you for your time.

Please rate from 0=very poor to 10=excellent

1. The overall quality of the 1st HS Academy Training Camp

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

2. Practical information on how to apply and the application process

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

3. Organization and timing of 1 HS-TC activities

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

4. The level of satisfaction with the content of the theory sessions

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

5. The level of satisfaction with the content of the practical sessions

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

6. Please provide further comments or suggestions (e.g.: What did you like most in the 1 HS-TC? What did you like least in the 1 HS-TC?)

ANNEX VI.

E-RIHS ETHICS GUIDELINES

Regardless of their field, those working with or as part of E-RIHS are expected to maintain the highest standards of professional integrity, competence, and compliance with all relevant codes of conduct and ethics. Ethics are important to E-RIHS, since the results generated through research are only as reliable as the strength of, and adherence to, the ethical values and principles underlying them. A strong ethical culture encourages an open, fair, respectful, and inclusive working environment, which permeates into relationships, and influences collective conduct. Finally, E-RIHS, which is humanist in nature and aims to study and preserve culture within the scope of heritage science, will likely have a societal impact on the values attributed to cultural heritage, public policies, and quality of life. Hence, there is a strong connection between the research infrastructure and ethics on many levels.

Although national and EU laws provide legislation to limit or ensure certain behaviours within each country and each E-RIHS provider institution, there are still a variety of behaviours that do not qualify as illegal but are inappropriate from an ethical standpoint. Many provider institutions already have their own set of guidelines and principles, which should also be adhered to. Since not all provider institutions may have such instruction and the E-RIHS community is diverse and continually expanding, the research infrastructure needs to provide a common understanding of ethical conduct. Therefore, these guidelines are not intended to replace existing local guidelines, but to complement them. Ethics within the E-RIHS providership is understood by a set of guidelines, by which all those working within its scope are bound to abide.

The E-RIHS ethical guidelines are constructed with the intention to minimise or, hopefully, eradicate unethical behaviours and practice in research. These guidelines will help to protect the credibility and reputation of E-RIHS. The guidelines have been composed in accordance with the All European Academies (ALLEA) Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. The ENVIRO report on Ethical Guidelines for RIs has been readily consulted and much of the ethical framework has been adopted here. As such, the ethical considerations of E-RIHS have been split into four ethical domains that reflect the levels various scales of ethical conduct: individual, interpersonal, societal, and environmental. For each domain, values considered intrinsic to the behaviour system outlined within the ethical guidelines will be presented and should be observed by all interacting with or, working within, E-RIHS.

VI.1 Individual Domain

Values: Honesty, Integrity, Transparency, Reliability, Competence

The value of the outputs produced by E-RIHS relies completely on the skills, abilities, honesty and integrity of those working for or collaborating with the RI. The quality of the research is closely related to personal skills, which must be maintained, reinforced, and developed to a high level of competence and professionalism. The reliability of E-RIHS research can be ensured by scientists agreeing to adhere to a set of ethical standards that reinforce academic integrity.

VI.1.1 QUALITY

Quality in all its forms should always be one of the pillars of scientific research. E-RIHS researchers and other professionals should strive to remain informed and apply the most recent advances in their field. This will require those working with or collaborating with E-RIHS to undertake regular lifelong training, during which they can continue to maintain and develop their understanding of research approaches. All those working within the context of E-RIHS should also receive training in research ethics and the RI's specific ethics principles to ensure adherence to the regulations described here.

Researchers should demonstrate meticulous organisation in planning, conducting, and participating in research projects, including using instruments of known accuracy and keeping complete laboratory registers. All relevant operations during any service to users under the E-RIHS brand should be covered by a register of dates, installations visited, persons present or contacted, operations or consultations and any other information needed for future reference. In particular, all measurements must be backed by sufficient information to allow an investigation of the causes of any anomaly and the eventual replication of all the experimental procedure (including any specific calibrations) in a different laboratory.

All digital or physical archived data must have a back-up made not more than a week after the original register. The back-up must be stored at a different physical or digital location to be preserved when for any fortuitous reason the original is lost.

While those working with or collaborating with E-RIHS should share ideas and information, they should maintain professional moderation in their conduct and publications, openly communicating limitations and uncertainties relating to the research.

VI.1.2 ACADEMIC INTEGRITY

Conflicts of interest should be disclosed at the earliest opportunity. Researchers should maintain the highest professional standards when designing, conducting, analysing and recording research. This means undertaking research in a well-considered, careful manner, which leads to a high level of accuracy within the results. Researchers should be open, transparent, honest, unbiased and have integrity in all stages of the scientific process.

Experimental procedures should be fully reproducible and the disclosure of results in scientific media should always include all information needed to replicate the experiments or measurements to a reasonable uncertainty. Reporting should include clarification on the use of external services or AI. Conclusions should be based on the critical and objective analysis of the evidence. Questionable conclusions should be presented as hypotheses and premature or exaggerated statements should be absolutely avoided. Scientific misconduct, such as bold or biased conclusions based on insufficient data, fabrication or plagiarism, are incompatible with E-RIHS' ethical principles.

VI.2 Interpersonal Domain

Values: Respect, Inclusivity, Equity, Reciprocity, Sharing, Cooperation, Safety

The interpersonal domain refers to the relationships formed between the personnel working within the research infrastructure, as well as the wider E-RIHS community. A respectful and inclusive working environment, in which cooperation, reciprocity, trust, and interdisciplinarity are prerequisites, is essential for achieving E-RIHS' shared goals. This can be accomplished by reducing

undue pressures that may lead to unacceptable behaviour and balancing professional competition with ethical values that contribute to good research practices.

VI.2.1 RESPECT FOR PERSONS

All those working for or interacting with E-RIHS are entitled to their rights as protected under all applicable laws and regulations. Researchers and other professionals should maintain the highest moral standards irrespective of the difficulties and limitations that might be raised at any moment. They should have concern for others and in general treat them as they would normally want to be treated in likewise conditions.

Professionals should comply with health and safety policies and procedures (and improve them when possible), to safeguard from undue risk and ensure the welfare of students, collaborators, all other team members and themselves. In line with the E-RIHS Risk Management Policy within D3.5 (Risk Management Strategy), this section should include an identification of hazards and a listing of risks. For each risk that may be controlled, the section will also indicate the countermeasures taken. Whenever the likelihood of a risk or the outcome of an occurrence may be reduced through information, the document will state how users are instructed on the avoidance of hazards and on how to address risks should they materialize. The document will also include a list of passive or active protection fixtures and countermeasures available and the contents will have in view, not only external users, but also all personnel involved.

Researchers should treat colleagues throughout the providership respectfully and as equals, fostering mutual understanding and encouraging professional courtesy in team working. They should share ideas openly, in the spirit of goodwill, whenever confidentiality of procedures or results is not at stake and give credit for the contributions of others. E-RIHS providers should participate in cooperative actions that diffuse knowledge by both teaching and learning.

Students should be given as much autonomy of decision in research as possible and treated with the same consideration due to colleagues, respectfully and without exploitation, having only in view the promotion of their learning and professional development in safety and without undue constraints.

VI.2.2 EQUALITY, DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

Professionals should behave without prejudice against others, treating them likewise irrespective of gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, age, sexual orientation, gender expression, presence of disabilities, educational background, professional origin or other personal attributes or aspects through which diversity manifests itself. Any behaviour or action contrary to the above, such as, discrimination, bullying, or harassment will not be tolerated.

Efforts should be taken to improve accessibility for individuals with disabilities, health conditions or impairments, which may mean making reasonable adjustments so that obstacles to participation are minimised.

VI.2.3 SAFEGUARDING

Tutelage of students or apprentices is to be regarded as a position of trust. Wherever possible, recognised intermediaries should be used so that students always have two different contact points, e.g., one tutor and one supervisor. This should be strictly adhered to whenever young people under the age of consent or individuals with reduced autonomy are involved.

VI.2.4 PEER REVIEW PROCESS

All activities and their outcomes are to be developed or handled in a fair way, transparent to all participants. Peer review panels should take seriously their responsibility to accurately judge applications, performance, or proposed publications. Whenever possible, there must be clear rules known to those being assessed and all notes should be clearly explained and justified. There should be an established system of appeal involving a third party. Registers of all consequential remarks and decisions should be maintained and made available to those deciding on any claims or appeals.

VI.2.5 ACKNOWLEDGING CONTRIBUTION

Users of E-RIHS are encouraged to disseminate the results of research undertaken via access to E-RIHS services in peer-reviewed publications, acknowledging the contribution and support provided by E-RIHS.

In accordance with good scientific practice, users are encouraged to offer co-authorship to those persons working at E-RIHS facilities who have made genuine scientific contributions to their work. E-RIHS recommends to all researchers within its providership to be generous with students and apprentices giving them, whenever fair, a position as authors that will enhance the development of their careers.

Authorship of papers and similar diffusion media should be based simultaneously on: i) substantial contributions to the conception of the research or the acquisition and interpretation of data for the work; ii) drafting the texts or revising them critically; and iii) approval of the version to be published in a way that makes the person fully accountable for the contents. Unless there is a clear preliminary understanding otherwise, only those meeting the three criteria should be deemed as authors or co-authors; all those not meeting the criteria but having nevertheless significant contributions should be acknowledged. The order of author names has a meaning that varies with the field but should follow clear rules known previously to all in writing and agreed between all team members. Ideally, papers should include an 'Author Contribution Statement' in the final publication.

As per copyright legislation and scientific custom, research outputs must necessarily refer to the persons or organisations, which have originally generated publications, data, or digital tools, or acknowledge the sources of the research lines being pursued.

VI.2.6 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

Before any project is started, the researchers involved must ensure that agreements are reached (ideally by a signed contract) regarding any research results and thereafter comply with defined practices for data use, ownership, sharing, and protection under intellectual property rights. By default, and as known to all and agreed between the team, a measure of confidentiality on processes and outcomes must be established before publication.

VI.3 Societal Domain

Values: Reputation, Trust, Stewardship, Service, Clarity

E-RIHS play a crucial role in bridging scientific knowledge and societal impact. It is aimed at generating and disseminating excellent science for cultural heritage, which may influence the values attributed to heritage, public policies, and quality of life. In fulfilling these duties, E-RIHS must ensure that its research has a positive impact, foster societal trust, and safeguard its reputation.

VI.3.1 STEWARDSHIP OF HERITAGE VALUES

Working with cultural heritage requires care and respect for the multitude of values that material heritage embodies. E-RIHS researchers and personnel should always collaborate with experts (curators, conservators and other) who can advise on issues and risks related to handling, transport and other aspects that arise during heritage science research. Such experts typically come from institutions entrusted with care for the cultural heritage in question.

The importance of tangible cultural heritage depends on a belief system that attributes significance and relative weight to an asset, be it a cathedral or a ring. A scientist will not put in question, in any manner, an established system of values unless grounded on largely unquestionable research results. Whenever research results contradict, in a relevant manner, values upon which the importance of a heritage asset rests (e.g., by strongly suggesting a different, more recent, chronology) those results must be reassessed. Eventually, the whole instrumental process should be repeated, possibly after a new sampling and by a different team using an alternate technology, before the results are published or made public in any manner. The owner or entity responsible for the asset will be informed in detail of the conclusions and their ground before any dissemination is made.

When analysing cultural heritage that has been removed from its culture of origin, collaboration with representatives from the originating culture is considered best practice, especially where objects are involved in repatriation discussions. Researchers should take time to listen and understand the significance of the object to the community of origin and be transparent about the potential impact of the analysis on the values ascribed to the cultural heritage.

VI.3.2 RESPONSIBLE SAMPLING

If no local institutional guidance exists, E-RIHS experts will abide by the Ethical Sampling Guidance developed by the UK Institute for Conservation (<https://www.icon.org.uk/resource/ethical-sampling-guidance.html>). Sampling for scientific research carries great responsibility due to object value, and when human remains are involved, there are also personal and sometimes religious issues to be aware of. In the selection of the number of samples and their size, and indeed locations where samples could be taken, as well as in all aspects related to the related decision processes, E-RIHS researchers will follow the Ethical Sampling Guidance to avoid any potential risk, reputational or otherwise, to E-RIHS and themselves.

Any sampling of a tangible heritage asset will decrease its value, even if negligibly. Therefore, it must be carefully considered on a basis of potential gain versus potential harm. Sample sizes must be adequate given the asset sampled and the purpose: as small as possible but not so small that they may end up being unfit.

When sampling a physical asset researchers will first seek consent from the owner or the entity responsible for its conservation. On seeking authorization, they will inform on the objective, number and size of samples needed, and method of sampling. They will also establish an agreement on the ultimate destination of the test items and any remainders.

In all cases, the owner or the entity responsible for the conservation will be offered the possibility to witness the sampling procedure and thenceforward be considered primary stakeholders of the research, be informed of the results before any dissemination and, if not co-authors, their participation will be acknowledged in publications using the results.

Samples of heritage assets, test items obtained thereof, and remainders are themselves heritage assets with associated values and must be treated as such, in particular caring that all information related to the sampling is obtained and kept traceable to each sample.

If applicable, scientists should aim at the preservation of test items and remainders associated with the information pertaining to the sampling and instrumental procedures applied, towards their future availability for further research without the need to re-sample. This will also broaden the possibilities of ARCHLAB.

VI.3.3 BENEFICENCE (DO GOOD)

The definition of beneficence is linked with outcomes that are beneficial to others and to the society at large. This principle states that research should aim at some positive outcome that will advance knowledge and our understanding of phenomena under the rule of science, towards a positive purpose such as the enhancement of some of the values of cultural heritage or the improvement of heritage science training provision. To ensure that research activities are beneficial to society, it is important that those working with or collaborating with E-RIHS weigh up the potential risks and societal implications of their research and mitigate possible negative impacts.

Researchers must take accountability for the research and its wider societal impact. Results should be shared with the research community, decision-makers, and the public at large through diffusion media, with clear explanation regarding errors, probabilities, and uncertainties. Public comments on scientific matters should be made with care and accuracy to avoid misunderstandings and misuse. Questionable conclusions should be presented as hypotheses and premature or exaggerated statements should be absolutely avoided. When talking to the media as a representative of E-RIHS, professional comments must be clearly distinguished from personal opinions.

E-RIHS personnel or users of services must be aware of the role they play in the sequence from academic research, pre-practice research, and practical implementation in management or decision-making. Conclusions made under one context may be misleading and ultimately detrimental, sometimes grievously, when applied in a specific situation. Therefore, researchers should not suggest or propose practical application with insufficient data validation and lack of practical demonstration.

VI.3.4 DATA LIFECYCLE

Data management within E-RIHS must adhere to the FAIR principles, emphasising findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Researchers must follow a Data Management Plan for data generation, management, and protection, ensuring reproducibility and accountability. Researchers must retain data, metadata, protocols, code, and other research materials.

E-RIHS plays a crucial role in data stewardship and preservation. Primary data preservation involves correct storage, documentation, and processing. Comprehensive metadata, including provenance and quality, ensures interoperability with other databases. E-RIHS will use Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs).

Balancing openness and accessibility with necessary restrictions is key. E-RIHS must avoid improper data use. Where data is accessible to non-expert users, clear descriptions of potential uses and limitations should accompany it. The manipulation of sensitive data for personal, media, industrial, or commercial purposes should be prevented by access and security policies.

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VI.3.5 PERSONAL DATA

Those working as part of E-RIHS must treat personal data responsibly, following the EU GDPR regulation. Data must be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently. When personal data is obtained, personnel must have a valid reason for processing data, and individuals should be informed about its use.

VI.4 Environmental Domain

Values: Awareness, Efficiency, Sustainability, Protection, Innovation

E-RIHS must be acutely aware of the interaction between scientific research and the natural environment. The RI has a responsibility to limit its impact on climatic change, ecosystems, and biodiversity.

VI.4.1 Do No SIGNIFICANT HARM

In line with the European Green Deal objectives, research and innovation activities should comply with the 'do no significant harm' (DNSH) principle according to which the research and innovation activities should not be supporting or carrying out activities that make a significant harm to any of the six environmental objectives ('climate change adaptation', 'climate change mitigation', 'sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources', 'pollution prevention and control', 'transition to a circular economy', and 'protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems'), within the meaning of Article 17, on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment (EU Taxonomy Regulation).

In practical terms, E-RIHS personnel and users should comply with all environmental standards, including the disposal of waste and waste products having in view, not only immediate consequences, but also possible risks in the long run. They should also carefully weigh up the environmental impact, cost, and safety of different methods of travel before booking transport to services, training, meetings, or conferences. The suitability of virtual meeting or events should be considered whenever possible. Those working within E-RIHS should always be mindful of efficiency and the minimisation of waste in relation to materials and resources.

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